

Grain loss due to earhead-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* larvae. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Calculated loss (t/ha)	Percent yield loss due to larvae
R35-2750	4.91	0.36	7.4
R35-2751	4.71	0.49	10.5
R35-2752	4.87	0.30	6.2
R-2384	4.20	0.39	9.4
RP-9-4	4.61	0.31	6.8
RPW6-12	4.31	0.26	6.1
BKN680-52	1.56	0.34	22.0
ORS-GR-181	2.95	0.50	16.8
W-13400	4.03	0.27	6.8
RPW6-17	5.69	0.20	3.6
Surekha	3.87	0.36	9.3

All the varieties suffered damage from larvae of the earhead-cutting caterpillar.

Grain loss varied from 0.20 to 0.50 t/ha, which was 3.6 to 22.0% of production. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

A simple method to characterize rice root systems in relation to drought resistance

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According to surveys by economists and anthropologists, rainfed rice farmers believe there is a correlation between the force required to pull seedlings in the seedbed and a variety's drought resistance. This intuitive relationship prompted us to devise a technique to measure this force, test various cultivars, and compare the information with current dry season drought field screening results.

We found that the pulling force could be estimated by the use of a hand-held spring balance with maximum reading indicator and a clamp device fabricated from aluminum and provided with soft rubber or fine sandpaper pads to grip the seedling (Fig. 1).

The ratio of varietal variance to total variance was greatest about 35 days after the entries were direct seeded into a well-puddled soil.

Care in site selection, soil preparation, thinning to single plant per hill, and minimizing border effects between hills

sampled all helped decrease sampling variation. Variation within the test varieties required 4 replications with 8 observations per replication to attain a CV of 10% or less. With experience, this sampling requirement should decrease.

The table illustrates the varietal differences among 20 selected varieties recently tested at IRRI in the 1980 dry

Varietal differences in the force required to pull up 40-day-old seedlings from puddled soil seed bed. MGL2 and IR20 are check varieties. IRRI, 1980 dry season. Entries connected by a common line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Variety or line	Root pulling force (kg)
MGL2 (check)	28.7
IR5853-198-1-2	26.8
IR5853-118-5	25.8
IR5853-162-1-2-3	23.1
IR5853-165-1-1-2	22.7
IR42	22.7
IR442-2-58	20.0
Nam Sagui 19	19.4
IR8	19.0
RD8	19.0
RD19	18.8
RD6	18.2
RD9	18.0
KDML 105	18.0
IR36	17.5
RD1	17.1
RD7	16.6
TN1	16.2
RD4	15.9
IR20 (check)	12.8

season. Field screening results from dry season upland trials are correlated with the root pulling force (Fig. 2), illustrating the value of this technique as a drought screening tool for use at

1. Instrument scale with heavy duty handle and clamp device used to measure force (kg) required to pull rice plants from the soil. IRRI, 1980.

2. Relationship between pulling force of several rice varieties and their drought resistance score at three progressively severe soil moisture levels (-2, -4, and -10 bar soil matric potential at 15-cm depth) in dry season upland field drought screening at IRR. 1980.

irrigated sites where special field or greenhouse drought-screening facilities are not available.

This technique should also find application as an indicator of variety suitability to other problems that affect

root system development such as tolerance for problem soils, insect or disease resistance, or the effect of agronomic practices such as direct seeding or root zone application of fertilizer. ■

Method for screening rice seedlings for drought tolerance during rapid generation advance

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Rapid generation advance (RGA) shortens the growth duration of a population and conserves the potential variability of a given cross. If selection of desirable types becomes possible during RGA, the produced materials would be of greater value to the breeders. Methods for screening varieties for cold tolerance and submergence tolerance at the seedling stage during RGA have already been developed. This study was undertaken to develop a method for screening drought tolerance at the seedling stage without delaying the flowering of the rices under RGA.

Of the traits required for photoperiod-sensitive rices for rained wetland areas, seedling drought tolerance in broadcast-seeded rice is important to ensure stand establishment. In deepwater areas where rice is grown by broadcasting seeds in dry soil, the seedlings invariably suffer from water stress. Sometimes the whole crop is reseeded because mortality due to water stress is high. Thus, it is imperative that the rices for these areas have drought tolerance.

The reproducibility of several greenhouse techniques for screening rices for drought tolerance encouraged US to develop a corresponding technique for use at the seedling stage of plants in RGA.

The procedure follows:

1. Sow pregerminated seeds 2 to a pot. (Ten varieties with known reactions to drought were used in the preliminary tests. The pots were 5.2 cm in diameter and 5.0 cm high with bottom drainage holes. Fertilizer was added at the rate of 2 g each of solophos and muriate of

potash per 4 kg of soil. Each pot contained 70 g soil.)

2. Place the pots in a box lined with plastic for ease in maintaining flooded conditions during the growth of the plants.

3. After 5 days of germination, thin to 1 plant/pot.

4. Apply ammonium sulfate at the rate of 35 mg/pot at 14 and 35 days after sowing. The later 3 successive top-dressings can be applied at 15-day intervals.

5. Raise the seedlings under well-watered conditions until 18 days after sowing and then withhold water for 5 days.

(In the RGA greenhouse [27 to 38°C], withholding of water longer than 5 days killed most of the varieties used. The moisture content of the soil at 7 days of moisture stress was 8.7%. In cooler climates, a longer stress period may be necessary. Accurate measurement of drought stress is not necessary; the important thing is to be able to eliminate the susceptible lines during RGA.)

6. Rewater the plants after 5 days of treatment and score for percentage of survival of the population or select the surviving plants 7 days after rewatering.

7. Remove the dead plants to decrease the space needed for growing the surviving plants.

8. After scoring the plants, start the short-day treatment.

The results of the tests showed that drought stress did not delay flowering; however, it reduced plant height, panicle length, and panicle weight, and increased spikelet sterility. During RGA such plant characters are relatively unimportant because no selections based on them are made. ■

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